

AN OVERVIEW OF THE HISTORY OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCIES

Rustambekova Nigora Abduganisovna

Tashkent City Yashnabad District No. 454 Dmtt Director

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8070192>

ANNOTATION

Human competencies take over result in it of individual qualities development directly depends being , this citizenship competence development in the process individual characteristics of students in consideration received without to build necessity shows . That's why for social active citizenship competence content of a person individuality concept point of view in terms of seeing exit is necessary .

Key words: *active citizenship, " component ", " competence ", competent approach ;*

Competencies efficient take over from the conditions one , human individual qualities all fields to develop service do , therefore for we social active citizenship competencies in development to the individual characteristics of students appeal we did and in our article light up we gave

Social active citizenship competence - in society happening _ incident and to processes a sense of belonging and them active participation to achieve , own citizenship duty and rights to know , to him compliance to do , to work and in civil relations treatment and legal to culture have to be formation of abilities mean holds

National and universal competence - to the motherland loyal , kind to people and universal and national to values religious to be , artistic art his works understand, between dress , cultural to the rules and healthy life style action to do abilities to form mean holds .

Social active citizenship competence development pedagogical and psychological aspects according to different approaches there is being , this approaches based on citizenship society formation with organic in dependence society to build and fair society about Central Asia , CIS countries and abroad scientists by take went scientific in research basically east waking up period scientists in the 9th-15th centuries the state manage and fair society build , state leader and of servants activity classifications , social responsibility criteria theoretical aspects about ideas of Abu Nasr Farabi , Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Nizamulmulk, Amir Temur , our republic from scientists NAMuslimov , BXXodzhayev , **foreign** countries from scientists Dj.Raven , B.Gershunsky , Dj.Raven and others in his work wide analysis done .

Our research as a result in students social active citizenship competence development pedagogical and psychological aspects , development factors , the main concepts their social significance and our country in development each one of the person responsibility , individual private qualities shaping through in students social active citizenship competence shaping possible our article in the content light up we gave

Abu Nasr Al- Farabi (870-950) " Fazil people city " , " State of the character aphorisms " in his works oriental political and legal and social thought in history social system , politics , state and the government about views theoretical based on By Abu Nasr Farabi according to

fair the state enlightened the ruler governs , it is spirituality , justice leader to be , own personal qualities with strictly requirements answer to give need saying thought means _

According to Abu Ali Ibn Sina (980-1037). social relationships people between difference and inequality looks as a result . Ibn Sina " economic and social and personal properties according to inequality is human social activity reason is " , he says . An ideal state to build while society of the population spiritual and moral development with it depends _ His It is said that it is spiritual moral of values high appreciation not only each bilaterally well-being , perhaps in society justice and also provides stability .

Nizamulmulk's work " Policy " officials morality qualities looking choice , justice and honesty leg under who does people state to work not to interfere with the state in management council with take go , activities regularly control to do , to obey , to perform and qualities about views with is important _ thoughts of our ancestors state of construction fair procedures attention because he gave is evidence .

Owner Amir Temurin the following thoughts present time with breathless : " Experience ," he writes to me that's it showed that religion and to the law not relied upon government , its great power long time save get up ca n't Him each how evil person entrance possible has been neither roof , no door , no bars there is home simile can.

That's why for I own my kingdom islam arches and in management myself strictly action doer laws based on I built ". The owner is Amur Temur according to the state in management the most important legality is the law priority . " Strictly order and to laws action to do my happiness the key it's done . General laws as religious the rules and they are based on written thoughts knew _ Of this all of them great Temur fair and virtuous to management separately attention that he focused showing is standing

Modern in society our country specialists by student take over possible has been knowledge , skill , skill , practical activity experience and competencies appropriation as a result active citizenship competencies shaping own as relevant remains.

N. A. Muslimov of the concepts of " competence " and " competence " . etymological to the analysis stops it is Competence - knowledge , qualification and personal qualities known in the field successful activity for apply get , competence the concept of " person certain education direction or specialty according to received knowledge , skill and skills and formed personal characteristics work in the activity successful apply get ability ," he expressed .

References:

- 1.<https://azkurs.org/informatika-va-akhborot-tekhnologiyalari-fani-orta-talim-barcha.html?page=13>
- 2.https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/pedagogical-psychological-possibility_of_developing_socially-active-citizen-competencies_in_students
- 3.<https://www.fayllar.org/2-amaliy-mashgulot-mavzusi.html?page=6>
- 4.<http://hozir.org/kommunikativ-kompetensiya.html?page=2>